

Chemical constituents of *Oroxylum indicum* roots and *Urena lobata* roots

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Abstract : Baicalein, chrysin, oroxylin A, baicalein-6-*O*-glucoside, β -sitosterol and its 3-*O*-glucoside, stigmasterol-3-*O*-glucoside from the root bark of *Oroxylum indicum*; β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol and their 3-*O*-glucosides from the roots of *Urena lobata* were isolated. The isolation of baicalein-6-*O*-glucoside, β -sitosterol and its glucoside and stigmasterol glucoside from the roots of *O. indicum* and all the steroids from the roots of *U. lobata* are reported for the first time. All these known constituents were identified by detailed spectroscopic studies. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR data of baicalein-6-*O*-glucoside pentaacetate is reported.

Keywords : *Oroxylum indicum*, Bignoniaceae, flavonoids, steroids, *Urena lobata*, Malvaceae,

Introduction

The root bark of *Oroxylum indicum* Vent. (Fam : Bignoniaceae) is astringent and used in traditional system of medicine for treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery, sore-throat, lung and stomach disorder^{1,2}. The roots of *Urena lobata* Linn. (Fam : Malvaceae) are diuretic and used as an external remedy for rheumatism. Earlier investigations on the root bark of *O. indicum* reported³ the isolation of baicalein, chrysin, oroxylin A, biochanin A and ellagic acid and on roots of *U. lobata* reported⁴ furocoumarin, imperatorin. In the present study, we have isolated four flavonoids and three steroids from the root bark of *O. indicum* and six steroids from the roots of *U. lobata* and their structural characterization is described herein.

Air-dried powdered root bark (1.5 kg) of *O. indicum* (collected from Ambasa, Dhalai District, Tripura in January, 2007) was extracted with MeOH (6 L) at room temperature by percolation process. The concentrated extract (85 g) was suspended in a little water (ca. 30 mL) and fractionated into hexane, dichloromethane, chloroform and *n*-butanol soluble fractions. The hexane fraction (3.5 g) on silica gel column chromatography (CC) afforded β -sitosterol (15 mg), C₂₉H₅₀O (M⁺ 414), m.p.

138 °C, characterized by comparison of its physical constants and spectral (IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and MS) data with literature⁵. The CH₂Cl₂ fraction (5.6 g) on silica gel CC afforded bright yellow needles (45 mg), m.p. 204–205 °C, C₁₆H₁₂O₅ (M⁺ 284), characterized as oroxylin A (1) by comparison of its physical constants and spectral (UV, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and MS) data with literature^{6,7}. The CHCl₃ fraction (6.5 g) on silica gel CC afforded yellow needle crystals (75 mg) from CHCl₃-EtOAc (7 : 3) eluate. It was characterized as chrysin (2), C₁₅H₁₀O₄ (M⁺ 254), m.p. 274 °C, by comparison of its physical constant and spectral (UV, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and MS) data with literature⁸. The elution of the column with CHCl₃-EtOAc (6 : 4) afforded brown needles (35 mg), C₁₅H₁₀O₅ (M⁺ 270), m.p. 262 °C, characterized as baicalein (3) from comparison of its physical constant and spectral (UV, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and EIMS) data with literature⁸.

A part of the butanol fraction on CC through Diaion HP-20 and silica gel afforded a semisolid mass (150 mg) identified as baicalein 6-*O*-glucoside (4), C₂₁H₂₀O₁₀ [M⁺ 432] by comparison of its spectral data (UV, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR and FAB-MS) with literature⁹ as well as by preparation of its pentaacetate (4a) from Ac₂O and pyri-

dine at room temperature, amorphous powder, $C_{31}H_{30}O_{15}$ (M^+ 642); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$) : δ 7.13 (1H, s, H-3), 12.95 (1H, brs, HO-5), 7.0 (1H, s, H-8), 8.09 (2H, brs, J 8.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.60 (2H, t, J 8.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 7.64 (1H, m, H-4'), 5.71 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, H-1''), 5.13 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 9.0 Hz, H-2''), 5.40 (1H, t, J 9.0 Hz, H-3''), 5.03 (1H, t, J 9.0 Hz, H-4''), 4.19 (1H, m, H-5''), 4.13 (1H, dd, J 12.5 and 2.0 Hz, H-6''), 4.39 (1H, dd, J 12.5 and 4.5 Hz, H-6''), 1.98, 2.00, 2.01, 2.02 and 2.24 (each s, 5 \times Ac); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$) : δ 164.4 (C-2), 105.6 (C-3), 182.6 (C-4),

- 1 R = OMe, R' = OH
 2 R = H, R' = OH
 3 R = R' = OH
 4 R = OGlc, R' = OH
 4a R = OGlc(Ac)₄, R' = OAc

152.1 (C-5), 126.5 (C-6), 154.1 (C-7), 97.0 (C-8), 154.1 (C-9), 106.5 (C-10), 130.6 (C-1'), 126.6 (C-2',6'), 129.3 (C-3',5'), 132.5 (C-4'), 105.6 (C-1''), 70.1 (C-2''), 71.6 (C-3''), 68.0 (C-4''), 71.4 (C-5''), 63.2 (C-6''), 19.84, 20.4 \times 2, 20.5 \times 2, 168.1, 169.3, 169.4, 169.6, 170.01. The NMR data of the acetate was reported for the first time. Another part of the BuOH extract on silica gel CC gave a light brown solid (35 mg), m.p. 268 °C (dec) characterized as a mixture of β -sitosterol glucoside (5) and stigmasterol glucoside (6) (7 : 3) by LC/MS analysis¹⁰⁻¹².

Air dried roots of *U. lobata* (0.5 kg) were extracted with MeOH (2.5 L) by percolation process. The concentrated MeOH extract (25 g) was fractionated into petroleum ether, chloroform and *n*-butanol soluble fractions. Only the chloroform fraction contained a substantial amount of residue (8.5 g) and was subjected to silica gel CC. The $CHCl_3$ eluate of the column afforded white shin-

ing crystals (35 mg), m.p. 138–152 °C, characterized as a mixture of β -sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol (54.7 : 34.5 : 10.8) by co-GC analysis with authentic samples as well as comparison of (IR, NMR and MS) spectral data of the crystals with literature^{13,14}. The EtOAc eluate of the column afforded white flake-like solid (45 mg), m.p. 265 °C (dec), identified as a mixture of glucosides of β -sitosterol (5), stigmasterol (6) and campesterol (7) (59.7 : 27.9 : 12.4) by LC/MS analysis and comparison of spectral (IR, 1H and ^{13}C NMR and MS) data of the solid with literature^{11,12}.

- 5 R = Et
 6 R = Et, Δ^{22}
 7 R = Me

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